

Integration of Real Colour Reconstruction for DCH Objects within an SfM/MVS Workflow

A straightforward, non-iterative, non-Deep Learning, non-NeRF-based approach to diffusive reflectance reconstruction under uncontrolled lighting conditions.

Abstract: *Reconstructing the physical optical properties of a material is a complex challenge. We present a method to extract the intrinsic diffusive colour in a straightforward and non-iterative manner, leveraging Global Illumination rendering techniques and tools already embedded in the SfM/MVS acquisition workflow. The approach starts from the apparent colour and IBL-based illumination to achieve accurate colour reconstruction.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Reconstructing the intrinsic colour of a physical surface is a key issue in various fields, ranging from pigment identification and medical diagnostics to the monitoring of environmental variables related to colour changes. This brings us to our specific area of interest: determining the intrinsic colour of digitized physical objects acquired through photogrammetry. The related theory and techniques fall within a hybrid domain, encompassing not only digitization methodologies but also the optical physics of materials and their modelling for computer graphics applications.

The problem becomes particularly complex for non-ideal physical objects, as the Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) varies at each point on the surface. This variation depends not only on the angle of the incident light and the observer's position but also on all the parameters used in different BRDF models, such as Roughness, Metalness, Albedo, Normals, Specularity, Emission, and others. Furthermore, this variation is typically not continuous. As a result, the BRDF is defined within each discrete unit into which the surface is subdivided, and the overall material behaviour is described by the sum of all discrete BRDF functions.

Computer graphics, as an implementation of mathematical models that describe the physical behaviours of objects, lights, and materials, provides the ability to manipulate these behaviours, offering immediate feedback and visualization of how digital models behave. The usefulness of CG, therefore, extends beyond the mere simulation of virtual environments for visualization purposes. It can also be employed to study and solve complex physical problems, particularly in optical physics, such as the reconstruction of an object's intrinsic colour, which is the focus of this study.

1.1 CONTEXT

As part of the activities conducted by Spoke 4 of the extended partnership [CHANGESs], Work Package 3 focuses on the large-scale 3D digitization of objects from museum and art collections, classifying them as Digital Cultural Heritage Objects (DCHO). Additionally, it includes the digitization of the environments and exhibition setups in which these objects are displayed. This context imposes operational constraints that frequently hinder the possibility of conducting acquisitions in controlled,

optimized settings. As a result, it has been necessary to develop specific guidelines (Bordignon et al., 2024).

This issue first emerged during a pilot case involving the digitization of the visitor experience at the temporary exhibition "The Other Renaissance: Ulisse Aldrovandi and the Wonders of the World", held in Bologna at SMA Palazzo Poggi from December 8, 2023, to May 28, 2024 (Balzani et al., 2024). Museum collection objects manipulation is problematic, and the large-scale acquisition of the 401 assets making up the exhibition, given its temporary nature and the presence of loaned items, would have made it impossible to set up controlled environments for optimal acquisition. This was particularly true for immovable objects, which had to be captured without the possibility of controlling lighting, except through partial mitigation strategies.

In such an operational context, the already complex challenge of reconstructing an object's intrinsic colour is further complicated by adverse factors such as mixed colour temperatures from different light sources and ambient lighting, as well as concentrated lights creating cast shadows and reflections. These conditions make it impossible to apply photogrammetry-integrated strategies such as preliminary colour correction (Gaiani et al., 2017) and shadow removal (Cipriani, Fantini, and Bertacchi, 2014).

Given these constraints, a deliberate decision was made not to reconstruct the intrinsic colour of the acquired objects, considering that the final product was intended to replicate the museum experience, where the use of apparent colour is a valid alternative to rendering the textured object with its intrinsic colour and then simulating it within a reconstructed synthetic lighting setup. However, the absence of intrinsic colour limits the reusability of DCHOs in contexts requiring relighting.

1.2 RESEARCH QUESTION

This led to the need to investigate whether it is possible to develop a method for reconstructing the intrinsic colour of acquired objects, particularly immovable ones subject to suboptimal lighting conditions, which can be seamlessly and efficiently integrated into the photogrammetric acquisition workflow. This inquiry can be summarized in the following research question: How can the intrinsic colour of immovable objects be reconstructed within the SfM/MVS acquisition workflow under any lighting conditions, without requiring prior colour calibration?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Three-dimensional modelling and the synthetic representation of material behaviour through images have made it possible to tackle the problem of reconstructing the reflectance of a physical object. This has been achieved by using digital images acquired from a real-world setup as the initial dataset, alongside the 3D digitization of the object, lighting modelling, and algorithms capable of accurately describing the physical interaction between digital lighting and material properties.

Building on the pioneering work of Nayar, Ikeuchi, and Kanade (1991)—who simplified the problem by assuming a single light source in the scene and a perfectly Lambertian convex object—Debevec (1998) introduced a pioneering methodology in his seminal paper "Rendering Synthetic Objects into

Real Scenes." This method included, as an intermediate step, the reconstruction of an object's reflectance by using a digital model of a complex scene illuminated by a high dynamic range (HDR) image, leveraging his previous work (Debevec & Malik, 1997), which outlined the technique for generating HDR maps from multi-exposure images.

This approach was later extended by Yu, Debevec, and Malik (1999) for more complex environments, where the assumption that synthetic objects do not interact with their surroundings no longer held. Consequently, the entire scene was modelled in 3D and divided into discrete sections, with each section's albedo estimated from the radiance of the surfaces in the scene through an Inverse Global Illumination algorithm.

Subsequently, other researchers (Gibson, 2001; Boivin, 2001) also adopted Inverse Global Illumination methods, which are analytical approaches. Yu and Malik (1998), on the other hand, proposed a technique based on capturing multiple images of the same scene under different lighting conditions, comparing them with synthetic images generated from a 3D model and an initial reflectance hypothesis, which was then iteratively refined to converge on an optimal solution. Debevec (2004) employed a similar approach, with the key difference that lighting was not modelled using synthetic entities (such as the sun and sky) but instead through an IBL-based (Image-Based Lighting) approach. Furthermore, while Yu and Malik relied on a mathematical modelling approach, Debevec incorporated Inverse Rendering techniques. This alternative approach enabled Debevec to generate a 3D model that included a synthetic reflectance description in the form of a diffuse colour map, allowing for scene relighting and the seamless integration of synthetic objects.

As is immediately evident, these inverse optimization methods—particularly those based on Inverse Rendering (Barron & Malik, 2014)—are well-suited for Deep Learning applications, where reflectance is often extracted alongside object shape, even from single images (Yu & Smith, 2019; Li et al., 2020). More recently, the development of Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) has made it possible to reconstruct the spatial variation of the plenoptic function (Srinivasan et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021), enabling the full reconstruction of material behaviour, independent of object geometry.

3. METHODOLOGY

Our method builds on the work of Debevec (2004), Yu, and Malik (1998), leveraging recent advances in photogrammetric data acquisition and processing through Structure from Motion (SfM) and Multi-View Stereo (MVS) algorithms. These techniques generate apparent colour maps, which result from the interaction between lighting conditions and the material's intrinsic colour. Therefore, while the generated texture may appear photorealistic, the intrinsic colour of the surface remains implicit and cannot be directly extracted.

To address this limitation, our approach aims to recover the intrinsic colour of the surface by deriving it from the apparent colour and a known lighting model. This method allows for the separation of lighting effects from the material's inherent properties, provided that specific assumptions and sim-

plifications are applied. In this regard, our work follows the principles of inverse rendering, as introduced by Debevec (2004), but benefits from more advanced acquisition technologies, making it better suited to the specific application context that motivated this research.

Deep Learning-based approaches, while powerful, are costly in both design and implementation and do not naturally integrate into photogrammetric workflows. This issue is particularly evident in methods based on Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF), where radiance is modelled independently of 3D geometry, requiring post hoc geometric reconstruction through custom conversion processes. At present, these methods lack the precision and reliability necessary for accurate and detailed 3D textured models, which are an essential requirement for DCHO object acquisitions.

3.1 BASIC ASSUMPTIONS

One of the intrinsic limitations of the photogrammetric method is that it reduces the specular component of reflectance, which depends on both the direction of the incident light and the position of the observer. This specular information is redistributed unpredictably into the reconstruction of the diffuse component in each texel of the texture. For this reason, we assume that the material behaves as a perfect Lambertian surface, meaning that it consists only of a diffuse component.

A second necessary constraint is the assumption that the surrounding environment does not receive feedback from the object. In other words, illuminance must be independent of reflected radiance. Under this condition, it becomes valid to represent illuminance not through a three-dimensional model, but rather as an HDR spherical map. Consequently, illumination in the synthetic scene is resolved using an Image-Based Lighting (IBL) approach.

Finally, we assume that the object is immovable, a condition typically found in the intended application context.

3.2 TERMINOLOGY SPECIFICATION

The three fundamental physical quantities involved in this study are Irradiance $E_i(\lambda, x)$, which represents the radiant energy per unit area received at a point x for each wavelength λ ; Reflected Radiance $L_r(\lambda, x)$, which describes the luminous intensity emitted in all directions from the surface at point x for each wavelength λ ; and Spectral Reflectance $\rho(\lambda, x)$, which quantifies how much of the incident light is reflected at each wavelength λ .

These three quantities are related by the following equation, which is explicitly formulated in terms of Spectral Reflectance, our unknown variable:

$$\rho(\lambda) = (\pi L_r(\lambda)) / (E_i(\lambda))$$

However, in the context of acquisition methodologies, different terms are often used to refer to these same quantities, particularly when they are considered globally rather than at a single point. If we extend their definition over the entire visible light spectrum and across the entire surface of a physical object, we can identify the following equivalences: Irradiance corresponds to Incident Light, Reflected Radiance is referred to as Apparent Colour, and Reflectance corresponds to Intrinsic Colour. Additionally, within the domain of Computer Graphics, the terminology shifts again. Incident Light is commonly referred to as Illumination, which includes all light sources in the scene, whether they are

synthetic lights, emissive surfaces, or HDR maps used for Image-Based Lighting (IBL). The Diffuse Colour represents the intrinsic colour of a synthetic material before interacting with light, typically stored as a texture map applied to the 3D model. Finally, the resulting colour after the interaction of the diffuse colour with illumination, computed during rendering, is known as Shading. Throughout this study, we will use these three sets of terms interchangeably, depending on the context in which they are applied.

The validity of these equivalences stems from the fact that both Reflectance $\rho(\lambda)$ and Radiance $L_r(\lambda)$ are defined for a specific wavelength. Thus, in a three-component (RGB) system, these quantities can be represented at each point as a colour, where the Red, Green, and Blue components correspond to their respective intensity levels at their reference wavelengths.

This representation allows us to express both Reflectance and Radiance in a synthetic, visually interpretable form: when the RGB components are combined, they produce an arbitrary colour. This means that the apparent colour observed at each point on a surface is determined by the attenuation of the incident light, governed by the intrinsic colour, which acts as a scaling factor between 0 and 1. Moreover, in the case of Lambertian materials, the apparent colour does not change with the observer's position.

In computer graphics, this translates to the fact that the shading at each point on the texture map applied to a 3D model is determined by the illumination contribution multiplied by the diffuse colour of that point.

3.3 WORKFLOW

The proposed workflow has a dual application: on one hand, the method is designed for real-world implementation, while on the other, it has been extended to validate its robustness under controlled conditions. This extension relies on the generation of synthetic data, allowing for the isolation and analysis of the method's intrinsic limitations, independent of the complexities introduced by the digitization of physical objects. Furthermore, the use of a synthetic intrinsic colour enables a final comparison between the reconstructed intrinsic colour and the expected value at the end of the extended workflow. This comparison helps to identify and characterize any significant discrepancies.

3.4.1 Acquisition

The acquisition setup consists of two entities: the physical object and the surrounding environment. The former is digitized through multiple photographs, following a well-established and documented photogrammetric workflow, while the latter is captured using a 360° camera, which records the scene through multiple exposures. This process adapts the method introduced by Debevec (1996)—originally designed for constructing HDR environmental maps from single low-dynamic-range shots—to the use of 360° cameras. This adaptation allows for direct digitization of the environment without requiring the use of reflective spheres, which were necessary in Debevec's later, well-known study (Debevec, 2004).

Since the object is considered immovable, the operation must be performed at least twice, placing the camera as close as possible to the object on two opposite sides. This ensures that, during post-

processing, it is possible to reconstruct the equirectangular HDR map for IBL by combining the two individual HDR maps obtained from the multi-exposure shots. This composition is done in a complementary manner, eliminating from each HDR map the portion occluded by the object.

3.4.2 RAW processing and export

The three-dimensional model is generated from the acquired images using dedicated photogrammetric software such as Metashape. The process begins with the application of Structure from Motion (SfM) algorithms, which reconstruct the camera positions in space, followed by Multi-View Stereo (MVS), which directly generates the mesh from the Depth Maps computed in the SfM phase. The traditional approach, which involved an intermediate step of creating a dense point cloud via MVS, followed by Surface Reconstruction algorithms to generate the mesh, has been found to be less precise. The apparent colour map, along with the UV mapping definition that enables it to be applied as a texture to the reconstructed 3D model, is also processed within the same photogrammetric software. Finally, the 3D model with its associated texture is exported in FBX format.

The multi-exposure image sets captured with the 360° camera for the HDR environment map are imported into any raster image processing software or plugin capable of combining individual 8-bit images into a single 32-bit image, which is then saved in HDR format.

The textured model and HDR map are then imported into a 3D authoring software such as Blender, which includes a rendering engine capable of using Global Illumination algorithms. The textured 3D object is assigned a fully diffuse synthetic material, with the texture applied in the base colour slot. The HDR map is loaded as an environment lighting map.

3.4.3 Synthetic data

The previous sections 3.4.1 and 3.4.2 describe the operational procedures that would be conducted in a real-world application, which serves as a prerequisite for constructing the proposed method. However, to validate the method itself, we deemed it necessary to eliminate the influence of factors unrelated to the strict evaluation of its physical accuracy in terms of simulation, like SfM/MVS characteristic inaccuracies and gaps in both 3D reconstruction and textures or the varying and non-linear response curve of the sensors deployed by cameras used for acquisition.

Subsequently, for method validation purposes, synthetic data will be used instead of real-world data. The intrinsic colour will be predefined and used as a diffuse colour map applied to a synthetic 3D model, which will be UV-mapped in an optimized way to minimize seams.

Furthermore, as previously mentioned, defining the input data in advance, particularly the intrinsic colour, will allow for an additional validation phase at the end of the workflow. In this phase, the reconstructed intrinsic colour can be compared with the predefined reference value to identify discrepancies and analyse the underlying phenomena that may be responsible for them.

3.4.4 Synthetic setup rendering

In the synthetic digital scene, a 3D object is associated with a diffusive material whose diffuse colour is derived from the synthetic intrinsic colour map. The scene is illuminated using a synthetic HDR map for Image-Based Lighting (IBL).

A rendering of the textured synthetic object is then generated, producing synthetic shading as the result of the interaction between the intrinsic colour and the IBL illumination. This shading is mapped through baking, using the same UV set that was employed to apply the synthetic diffuse colour map (Fig. 1).

As a result, a synthetic textured 3D object is obtained, which is functionally equivalent to what would be achieved in a real-world application, where the acquisition and digitization of ambient illumination and a physical object would take place. This equivalence allows the workflow to transition seamlessly back to the normal process designed for real-case applications in the following sections.

3.4.5 Rendering with perfectly white and diffusive material

Given the setup just described, both irradiance (incident light), which is represented as an HDR map for IBL, and radiance (apparent colour), which is encoded as the shading colour for each texel in the corresponding map, are known. The reflectance (intrinsic colour), or more specifically, its diffuse colour component, remains unknown.

However, it is possible to use the 3D rendering engine to compute the apparent colour of the same object under the assumption that its diffuse colour is perfectly white (Fig. 2). This is equivalent to stating that its intrinsic colour is entirely white, and its reflectance is equal to 1, assuming that the material behaves as a perfect Lambertian surface.

Once the shading colour of the white-rendered object has been computed, it can be baked using the same UV set that was used to map the photogrammetric model.

This operation produces an apparent colour map that is perfectly aligned with the one obtained photogrammetrically, maintaining a pixel-to-pixel (and therefore texel-to-texel) correspondence, since the UV set remains identical.

3.4.6 Processing of Shading/Apparent Colour Maps

Both maps are imported into a raster image editing software, such as Photoshop. The maps are typically 8-bit, but if the brightness levels of the represented colours fall entirely within the dynamic range that can be represented by 8-bit images—without light and dark greys being compressed into pure white and black—it is possible to encode the images in 32-bit using a linear transformation.

Each map encodes the spectral radiance of the two versions of the same 3D model—the photogrammetric version and the white-rendered synthetic version—as RGB colour values per pixel. Since irradiance remains constant, the spectral reflectance of the acquired material can be computed for each RGB channel as the ratio between the brightness in the photogrammetric map and the brightness in the white synthetic map.

This operation can be performed by simply overlaying the two 32-bit maps in the raster editing software, using the "divide" blending mode (Fig. 3). Specifically, this operation follows the formula:

$$\text{Resulting pixel} = \text{Photogrammetric map pixel} / \text{White synthetic map pixel}$$

This ratio, at a physical level, directly corresponds to the previously established correct relationship between Reflectance, Radiance, and Irradiance:

$$\rho_{RGB}(X,y) = (L_{foto}(X,y)) / (L_{bianco}(X,y))$$

The unknown reflectance is thus straightforwardly computed as a diffuse colour map, which can then be reapplied to the 3D object using the same UV set employed throughout the process. This, in principle, allows for the visualization of the intrinsic colour of each texel of the object.

3.4.7 Discrepancy Evaluation and Validation

In a real-world application, the method concludes with the previous section (3.4.6). However, in the extended workflow described in this study, an additional validation phase is required to compare the reconstructed colour with the predefined synthetic reference. The discrepancies between the known reference colour and the one obtained through the process are analysed to assess the method's accuracy, allowing for the identification and characterization of significant variations that cannot be attributed solely to minor inaccuracies.

The discrepancy evaluation is also performed using raster image editing software, taking advantage of the pixel-to-pixel structural alignment between the synthetic intrinsic colour map and the reconstructed output map, a consistency ensured using the same UV set. The two maps are then overlaid using the Difference blending mode, producing an absolute difference map (Fig. 3) in which identical pixels appear black, while discrepancies are highlighted with an intensity proportional to the difference in each RGB channel.

The selected approach, in addition to being easily implementable using tools and software already integrated into the workflow, provides an immediate synthetic visual evaluation, enabling significant discrepancies to stand out from the background noise caused by minor variations in the map's colour synthesis.

4. CASE STUDIES

The method was applied to two synthetic test sets, each designed to isolate different material behaviours (Fig. 4).

The first test set consists of a sphere with parallel stripes in red, green, and blue, alternated with white stripes. The object is placed in a synthetic scene illuminated by two artificial light sources of complementary colours—green and violet—positioned on the equatorial plane of the sphere at a 120° angle from each other. The coloured stripes allow for a visual assessment of the material's response across individual RGB channels, while the white stripes help detect any unexpected colour shifts or dominant hues. Additionally, the 120° angle leaves part of the sphere in shadow, enabling an evaluation of the material's response to significantly diverse levels of reflected radiance.

The second test set is designed as a highly simplified stylization of the Mausoleum of Theodoric, chosen as a relatively complex object with radial symmetry. The model features recesses and protrusions, which generate secondary bounces in the Global Illumination (GI) solution, causing localized indirect self-illumination in response to direct lighting. The assigned material is predominantly

white, with subtle coloured inserts. The synthetic object is placed on a saturated green support surface to evaluate its influence and is illuminated using an Image-Based Lighting (IBL) source. The goal of this second test set is to assess the behaviour of a non-perfectly convex object under conditions closer to real-world operational.

5. OUTCOME ANALYSIS

The synthetic test sets generally confirm the validity of both the theory and the proposed method, with one notable finding: if the model is not perfectly convex or flat, surface areas where the Normals are convergent generate mutual contributions of self-illumination from bounces beyond the second order of the rays emitted by the IBL source (Fig. 5). In the case of coloured objects, this results in an apparent colour contribution that is not entirely determined by irradiance.

In the white synthetic version, this spectral luminance variation cannot be replicated. Consequently, the reflectance expressed in the diffuse colour map exhibits colour variations complementary in hue to the real object's colour at the surface points that contributed to the apparent colour.

6. FUTURE WORK

As previously stated, the proposed method has been specifically designed for seamless integration into an SfM/MVS photogrammetric workflow for the acquisition of 3D Digital Cultural Heritage Objects (DCHOs), with the aim of publishing them as 3D assets optimized for Web3D applications.

It has, therefore, been conceived for practical applications and will require further refinement to ensure a broad and effective scope across various challenges. Many of these challenges are already known at this preliminary validation stage of the general method, both from a physical standpoint and in terms of computer graphics.

In addition to these known issues, as well as the findings from the synthetic case studies, we assume that further challenges may emerge. Only through the development of a methodology for the practical application of the proposed method to real-world cases will we be able to fully identify these potential issues.

Operational workarounds and mitigation strategies can also be devised for known and anticipated challenges in the photogrammetric acquisition process. For example, efforts could be made to minimize the impact of the specular component in materials that are not perfectly Lambertian.

Furthermore, methodological precautions must be introduced in the data processing phase to maintain control over all procedural steps once the data no longer incorporate the simplifications applied during the generation of synthetic data. Key concerns include colour management in conversions, consistency of data acquired with different instruments and software, and the outcome of data processing.

Lastly, it will be necessary to define the operational procedure for applying the general method, to assess its usability in real-world scenarios and characterize its limitations.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been partially funded by Project PE 0000020 CHANGES - CUP B53C22003780006, NRP Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.3, Funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU"

Conflicts of Interest disclosure

The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

Bordignon, A. et al. (2024). *Guidelines for the digitisation of museum and art collections*. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14249936.

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14249936> (accessed 06/02/2025)

Balzani, R. et al. (2024). *Saving temporary exhibitions in virtual environments: The Digital Renaissance of Ulisse Aldrovandi—Acquisition and digitisation of cultural heritage objects*. *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage*, 32, p.e00309.

Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212054823000541> (accessed 06/02/2025)

Gaiani, M. et al. (2017). *Securing color fidelity in 3D architectural heritage scenarios*. *Sensors*, 17(11), p.2437.

Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/17/11/2437> (accessed 06/02/2025)

Cipriani, L., Fantini, F. and Bertacchi, S. (2015). *El color en las piedras y en los mosaicos de Rávena: nuevas imágenes de los monumentos antiguos a través de la fotogrametría no convencional de última generación*. *EGA Expresión Gráfica Arquitectónica*, (26), pp.190-201.

Available at: <https://polipapers.upv.es/index.php/EGA/article/view/4052> (accessed 06/02/2025)

Nayar, S.K., Ikeuchi, K. and Kanade, T. (1991). *Shape from interreflections*. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 6, pp.173-195.

Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/BF00115695> (accessed 06/02/2025)

Debevec, P. (2008). *Rendering synthetic objects into real scenes: Bridging traditional and image-based graphics with global illumination and high dynamic range photography*. In *ACM SIGGRAPH 2008 classes*, pp. 1-10.

Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/1401132.1401175> (accessed 06/02/2025)

Debevec, P.E. and Malik, J. (2023). *Recovering high dynamic range radiance maps from photographs*. In *Seminal Graphics Papers: Pushing the Boundaries*, Volume 2, pp. 643-652.

Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3596711.3596779> (accessed 06/02/2025)

Yu, Y. et al. (1999). *Inverse global illumination: Recovering reflectance models of real scenes from photographs*. *Proceedings of the 26th annual conference on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques*, pp. 215-224.

Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/311535.311559> (accessed 06/02/2025)

Gibson, S. et al. (2001). *Flexible image-based photometric reconstruction using virtual light sources*. *Computer Graphics Forum*, 20(3), pp. 203-214.

Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/1467-8659.00513> (accessed 06/02/2025)

- Boivin, S. and Gagalowicz, A. (2001). *Image-based rendering of diffuse, specular, and glossy surfaces from a single image*. Proceedings of the 28th annual conference on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques, pp. 107-116.
Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/383259.383270> (accessed 06/02/2025)
- Yu, Y. and Malik, J. (1998). *Recovering photometric properties of architectural scenes from photographs*. Proceedings of the 25th annual conference on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques, pp. 207-217.
Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/280814.280874> (accessed 06/02/2025)
- Debevec, P. et al. (2004). *Estimating surface reflectance properties of a complex scene under captured natural illumination*. ACM Transactions on Graphics, 19, p.2.
Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Estimating-Surface-Reflectance-Properties-of-a-Debevec-Tchou/671bd7cc7f13b31b2f3899142546faddecf435fd> (accessed 06/02/2025)
- Barron, J.T. and Malik, J. (2014). *Shape, illumination, and reflectance from shading*. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, 37(8), pp.1670-1687.
Available at: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/6975182> (accessed 06/02/2025)
- Yu, Y. and Smith, W.A. (2019). *Inverserendernet: Learning single image inverse rendering*. Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, pp. 3155-3164.
Available at: https://openaccess.thecvf.com/content_CVPR_2019/html/Yu_InverseRenderNet_Learning_Single_Image_Inverse_Rendering_CVPR_2019_paper.html (accessed 06/02/2025)
- Li, Z. et al. (2018). *Learning to reconstruct shape and spatially-varying reflectance from a single image*. ACM Transactions on Graphics (TOG), 37(6), pp.1-11.
Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3272127.3275055> (accessed 06/02/2025)
- Srinivasan, P.P. et al. (2021). *Nerv: Neural reflectance and visibility fields for relighting and view synthesis*. Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, pp. 7495-7504.
Available at: https://openaccess.thecvf.com/content/CVPR2021/html/Srinivasan_NeRV_Neural_Reflectance_and_Visibility_Fields_for_Relighting_and_View_CVPR_2021_paper.html (accessed 06/02/2025)
- Zhang, X. et al. (2021). *Nerfactor: Neural factorization of shape and reflectance under an unknown illumination*. ACM Transactions on Graphics (ToG), 40(6), pp.1-18.
Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3478513.3480496> (accessed 06/02/2025)

List of Figures

Please enter the caption of each Figure and the desired width in the table below.

No.	Caption	Width (8 or 17 cm)
Fig. 1	3D view of "Sphere" set with diffuse colour applied	8cm
Fig. 2	3D view of "Teodorico" set with white colour applied	8cm

Fig. 3	Stacked HDR shading maps from "Teodorico" set	17cm
Fig. 4	Synthetic sets "Sphere" and "Teodorico" with real colour applied	17cm
Fig. 5	Colour bleeding from 2 nd bounced light on "Teodorico" set	8cm